

ABSTRACT BOOK

**International Congress on Nuclear Medicine,
Molecular Imaging and Molecular Therapy**
FROM IMAGE TO DIAGNOSIS & TREATMENT
Novi Sad April 19-20, 2024

Organizers:

Faculty of Medicine, University of Novi Sad
&
Academy of Medical Sciences Serbian Medical Society

Organizing Committee

Prof Jasna Mihailović, MD, PhD

Department of Nuclear Medicine, Faculty of Medicine, Novi Sad,
Oncology Institute of Vojvodina, Sremska Kamenica, Serbia

Assoc Prof Nataša Prvulović-Bunović, MD, PhD

Department of Nuclear Medicine, Faculty of Medicine, Novi Sad,
Oncology Institute of Vojvodina, Sremska Kamenica, Serbia

Dr Jelena Roganović, MD

Oncology Institute of Vojvodina, Sremska Kamenica, Serbia

Scientific Committee

Prof Stanley Goldsmith, MD, ScD (Hon), DMed (Hon)

Professor Emeritus in Radiology,
Professor of Medicine, Weill Cornell Medicine, New York City, USA

Prof Leonard Freeman, MD

Professor Emeritus, Montefiore Medical Center,
Albert Einstein College of Medicine, New York City, New York, USA

Prof Douglas Van Nostrand, MD

Professor of Medicine, Georgetown University School of Medicine,
Washington, USA

Prof Lisa Bodei, MD, PhD

Memorial Sloan Kettering Cancer Center, New York City, USA

Prof Ralph McCready, MD, PhD

Hon Consultant Nuclear Medicine, Royal Sussex County
Hospital Brighton, Brighton, UK

Prof Sonya Sergieva, MD, PhD

Sofia Cancer Center Sofia, Department of Nuclear Medicine, Sofia, Bulgaria

Prof. Zvezdana Rajkovača, MD, PhD

Department of Nuclear Medicine and Thyroid Gland Disease,
University Clinical Centre of the Republic of Srpska,
Faculty of Medicine Banja Luka,
Republic of Srpska, Bosnia and Herzegovina

Prof. Venjamin Majstorov, MD, PhD

Medical Faculty, Institute of Pathophysiology and Nuclear Medicine,
Skopje, North Macedonia

Prof Vladimir Obradović, MD, PhD
Head of Board of Directors, Clinical Centre of Serbia, Belgrade, Serbia

Prof Milovan Matović, MD, PhD
Polyclinic Joković, Kragujevac, Serbia

Prof Marina Vlajković, MD, PhD
Center of Nuclear Medicine, University Clinical Center Niš,
Faculty of Medicine, University of Niš, Niš, Serbia

Prof Vera Artiko, MD, PhD
Center for Nuclear Medicine with Positron Emission Tomography,
University Clinical Center of Serbia,
Faculty of Medicine University of Belgrade, Serbia

Prof Dragana Šobić Šaranović, MD, PhD
Center for Nuclear Medicine with Positron Emission Tomography,
University Clinical Center of Serbia,
Faculty of Medicine University of Belgrade, Serbia

Ass Prof. Dragan Pucar, MD, PhD
Institute for Nuclear Medicine, Military Medical Academy, Belgrade, Serbia

Dr Aleksandar Simić, MD
Special Hospital for Thyroid Gland and Metabolism Diseases Zlatibor, Serbia

Research Prof Sanja Vranješ-Đurić, PhD
Institute of Nuclear Science, Vinča, Serbia

PREDICTING EARLY RESPONSE TO RADIOIODINE THERAPY IN PAPILLARY THYROID CARCINOMA USING SUPERVISED MACHINE LEARNING APPROACH: A PILOT STUDY

Marina Popović Krneta¹, Dragana Šobić Šaranović², Ljiljana Mijatović
Teodorović^{1,4}, Zoran Bukumirić⁵, Tatjana Stanojković⁶, Ivana Pašić⁶,
Jadranka Antić⁷, Biljana Bazić Đorović¹, Miljana Tanić^{6,8}

¹Department of Nuclear Medicine, Institute for Oncology and Radiology of Serbia, Belgrade, Serbia

²University of Belgrade, Faculty of Medicine, Belgrade, Serbia

³Center for Nuclear Medicine with PET, University Clinical Center of Serbia, Belgrade, Serbia

⁴University of Kragujevac, Faculty of Medical Sciences, Kragujevac, Serbia

⁵Institute of Medical Statistics and Informatics, Faculty of Medicine, University of Belgrade, Serbia

⁶Department of Experimental Oncology, Institute for Oncology and Radiology of Serbia, Belgrade, Serbia

⁷Clinic for Endocrinology, Diabetes and Metabolic Diseases, University Clinical Centre of Serbia, Belgrade, Serbia

⁸UCL Cancer Institute, London, United Kingdom

Introduction: The three-tiered American Thyroid Association risk system primarily relies on data obtained from pathological analyses, overlooking other potential risk factors. This limitation hinders accurate prediction of occult, regional, or distant metastases after surgery. Since decisions on radioactive iodine (RAI) therapy often rely on this system, determining whether to administer therapy and deciding on the appropriate dosage becomes a challenging task. **Aim:** This pilot study assessed four machine learning (ML) classifiers to predict early responses to RAI treatment in PTC patients, aiming to identify those at higher risk of therapy failure. **Methods:** The classifiers were developed utilizing clinico-pathological, molecular, and laboratory data collected from 95 patients who underwent both surgical and RAI treatment. The therapy response assessment categorized patients into two groups: excellent response and RAI therapy failure, encompassing indeterminate, biochemical incomplete, and structural incomplete responses. The ultimate ML classifier was chosen based on the highest specificity and minimal overfitting, while maintaining high sensitivity. **Results:** Among the evaluated models, the k-Nearest Neighbor (k-NN) classifier emerged as the best fit, boasting an area under the receiver operating characteristic curve of 0.82 and sensitivity, specificity, positive and negative predictive values, and F2 score of 0.90, 0.45,

0.44, 0.91, 0.75. Notably, the most significant risk factors predicting RAI failure were the lymph-node ratio (LNR), and a postoperative stimulating thyroglobulin (sTg) level. A LNR exceeding 0.36 and a sTg level above 7.38 ng/ml predict a higher likelihood of RAI therapy failure. Conclusion: Our findings suggest that the k-NN model demonstrates potential in predicting early responses to RAI therapy, offering valuable insights into the significance of identified risk factors, such as lymph-node ratio and postoperative stimulating thyroglobulin levels.

Keywords: Papillary Thyroid Carcinoma, Radioactive Iodine Treatment, Machine Learning